
Environment and its influence

Observations on rice grown in submerged vs saturated hydroecosystems in Gangetic alluvial soils

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Some scientists believe that submergence of the field during the life span of the rice crop is essential to maximize reproductive as well as vegetative yields. Others have reported, however, that submergence is not essential to high yields. They believe that during the growing season, soil saturation at field capacity is also conducive to high rice production with little yield sacrifice under certain agroecologic conditions (a high water table and low evaporative demand). A field trial was conducted in the 1977 summer monsoon season in Gangetic alluvial soils (medium-textured) of the BHU research farm, Varanasi. The indica semidwarf Cauvery was grown in: 1) fields that were submerged at a depth of 3–5 cm, and 2) soil that was saturated at field capacity (0–0.1 atmospheric tension).

The rice plants in the submerged fields tillered heavily, had more foliage, and were taller than those grown in saturated soil. The leaves were shiny green, their functional area and functional duration were high. The plants headed and flowered 3 to 5 days earlier. The relative growth rate and dry-matter production were also superior. The roots proliferated in the undergrown soil profiles both vertically (26 cm) and horizontally (12 cm). The feeding roots were numerous and the root surface area was nearly double that of rice grown in saturated soil.

On the other hand, poor root proliferation of plants in saturated soil must have been due to the high mechanical impedance in such soil. The rice plants in saturated soil faced severe competition from mesophytic and

semiaquatic weed flora such as *Cyperus rotundus*, *Cyperus diffimis*, *Eclipta prostrata*, and *Cynodon dactylon*. In both submerged and saturated soils, the white, hollow roots of *Panicum repens* reached a distance of 30 cm in the soil within 2 weeks and the roots of *E. prostrata* occupied the entire feeding zone of the rice roots. *C. dactylon* was almost completely suppressed in the flooded soil, but neither *Panicum* sp. nor *Commelina benghalensis* was affected by moisture regimes.

Algal films were absent in the saturated soil, but algal flora flourished in flooded rice beginning at 4 days after transplanting. Nitrogen fertilization rapidly increased algal growth. As the crop canopy covered the field, the algal

blooms gradually disappeared (because of lack of light for photosynthesis). The algal films played a role other than nitrogen fixation – they suppressed the growth of aquatic weed flora by curtailing light penetration through the water surface. Another interesting phenomenon in the submerged-water regime was the low rice plant damage from mole crickets, cutworms, and rodents.

The plants grown in the saturated field showed wilting symptoms because cell turgidity decreased at midday on bright, sunny days. Grain yields were almost one third less under saturated conditions. Therefore, saturation at field capacity cannot substitute for flooding to maximize rice yields. □

Too late for

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Production of the perfect stage of the leaf scald fungus in culture

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In 1978 S. H. Ou and associates reported the natural occurrence of the perfect stage of the leaf scald fungus *Rhynchosporium oryzae* on rice in the Philippines, Colombia, and Costa Rica.

They compared descriptions of the fungi as reported by several authors, and concluded that the proper name of the perfect stage of the fungal causal agent of leaf scald was *Metasphaeria albescens* (von Thuemen) Wei.

Production of the perfect stage of most ascomycetes is a sexual recombination process that results in the formation of haploid, uninucleate

ascospores. Because *M. albescens* is an ascomycete, the same general reproductive features should apply so the individual ascospores can be genetically studied for pathogenicity and other race and cultural characteristics.

Rice leaves that exhibited typical leaf scald symptoms were collected at IRRI in August 1978. The leaves, which contained perithecia, were placed on the top cover of moist petri dishes. Ascospores were allowed to drop onto water agar (1.4%). Thirty-nine individual ascospores were transferred to agar slants. The single ascospore cultures were used as parents in various combinations. Ninety-six crosses or matings were attempted. Mycelial fragments and conidia were transferred from the monoascosporic cultures to nutrient solution and cultured at 25°C in the dark